

Argemone mexicana: A Comprehensive Review of its Pharmacological Properties

A. M. Krupanidhi, Aishwarya R. Kurdekar*, Prakash Dabadi

Department of Pharmacology, Bapuji pharmacy college , Davangere-577004 Karnataka, India.

Corresponding author

Aishwarya R. Kurdekar

Department of Pharmacology, Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davanagere-577004, Karnataka, India.

Dr. A M Krupanidhi

Department of Pharmacology, Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere-577004 Karnataka, India

Dr. Prakash Dabadi

Department of Pharmacology, Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere-577004 Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

Argemone mexicana a member of Argemone genus within Papaveraceae family, is widely distributed plant in india and used to treat a wide range of illnesses. Many parts of the plant were utilized extensively in homeopathic, Siddha, Ayurvedic, and Unani treatments. The plant is a weed, easily available and it does not require any special care which forms the base to develop a drug in socio economic form so that it could be made available to all people. Chemical investigations of this plant have revealed that the presence of alkaloids, amino acids, phenolics and fatty acids. The present review includes the documentation of recent pharmacological properties and actions of whole plant extract of *Argemone mexicana* compiled from the databases such as Pub Med, Research Gate, Elsevier.

Keywords: *Argemone mexicana*, papaveraceae, pharmacological properties, Mexican prickly poppy, habitate, botany, extract.

1. INTRODUCTION

Plants have been used in medicines since time immemorial. India has a rich heritage of using medicinal plants in traditional medicines, as in the Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani systems besides folklore practices. As per Indian mythology most of Indian civilization have bank of traditional medicinal inadequate knowledge. Natural products are a source of new chemical diversity and are the choice of today's world. Nature itself gives remedy to all our health problems. The sources of natural product are plants, animals and microorganisms. We are having many side effects and long term complications in synthetic drugs. For that, the plant *Argemone mexicana* is a boon to the human being as it has a number of miraculous compounds to cure a various types of diseases. It is reported to have antimicrobial activity, wound healing property, larvicidal and chemosterilant activity, nematocidal and allelopathic potential, antimalarial, antibacterial and antifungal, molluscicidal, anticancer, hepatoprotective, anti-HIV and neuropharmacological activity.

Medicinal plants have ample of compounds which can be used to heal chronic as well as contagious diseases. Green plants are effective reservoir of chemotherapeutic agents that are non-phytotoxic, more systemic and easily biodegradable. Based on these benefits the present study is focused on review of research findings on *Argemone mexicana*.

2. PLANT PROFILE [2]

Table 1: Taxonomical Classification

Plantae Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida Dicotyledons
Subclass	Magnoliidae
Order	Papaverales
Family	Papavaraceae
Genus	Argemone
Species	A. mexicana

3. HABITATE AND BOTANY OF ARGEMONE MEXICANA

Argemone mexicana (Mexican poppy, Mexican prickly poppy, flowering thistle) is one kind of species of poppy found in Mexico and now widely grows wild in several parts of the world. It is an extraordinary weed which is indigenous in South America and also scattered in tropical and subtropical areas of the World including West Africa [3]. This plant is normal all over the place by fields and roadsides in India also [4]. *A. mexicana* is an erect annual herb that can grow upto 30–80 cm tall. It has a simple or only sparsely branched stem, a stalk, from which yellow latex oozes when mechanically damaged. The leaves are alternate, pinnate, without

petioles, and with spiny edges. The surface of the leaves has a blue-green color with light veins. Its appearance resembles a thistle. The flowers have a diameter of 4–8 cm, are Seed pods are prickly barrels in shape, hence, the name prickly poppy. The fruit is an elongated spiny capsule with a length of 2.5–4.5 cm and a width of 2 cm, which when ripe releases numerous small black and round oily seeds about 1 mm in diameter [5].

4. PHARMACOLOGICAL PROPERTIES

4.1 Wound healing action

Ghosh and his team investigated the latex's and *A. Mexicana* extract's in vivo wound-recovery properties. Their study's findings showed an impressive injury-recovery effect comparable to that of the equivalent standard, nitrofurazone [6]. *A. mexicana* leaves Extract showed prominent wound healing result with established drug nitrofurazone[7]. Using excision, incision, and dead space wound models in Wistar albino rats, methanol extract of *A. Mexicana* leaves tested for wound curative action, it showed better and faster wound curative action compared to petroleum ether, chloroform, and aqueous extracts of the leaves [8]. Wound recovering action using ointment of ethanolic root extract of *A. Mexicana* resulted in better healing potency compared with gentamycin (0.3% w/w) in Swiss albino rats [9]. Excision and incision wound models were used to assess the healing activity of the wounds. The *Argemone mexicana* fruit's crude extract was separated using distilled water, n-hexane, and ethyl acetate. Compared to the aqueous fraction extract and simple ointment treated groups, the n-hexane and ethyl acetate fraction treated groups had significantly greater wound contraction, a shorter re-epithelialization duration, and higher levels of fibrosis, neovascularization, and collagen tissue development[10].

4.2 Anti-inflammatory

Study of Sharma, S., and colleagues reported that, mice treated with an ethanolic extract of *A. mexicana* leaves at a dose of 200 mg/kg exhibited notable analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects [11]. The activity against the inflammation was evaluated by the preventive action of hypotonicity-induced HRBC membrane lysis. The findings indicated that the plant extract of *Argemone mexicana* has a strong anti-inflammatory effect and might be used as a treatment for inflammation [12]. The ethanol extract of *A. mexicana* roots was tested for its ability to prevent albumin-induced oedema in rats 50 and 100mg/kg and had a strong anti-inflammatory effect. After treatment, the greatest inhibitory effect was seen 40 minutes later [13]. Carrageenan-induced rat paw and cotton pellet-induced granuloma models were used to assess the anti-inflammatory efficacy. N-hexane, ethyl acetate, and distilled water were used to fractionate the crude extract of *Argemone mexicana* fruit. At the measured dose of 400 mg/kg, the ethyl acetate fraction demonstrated a significant percent edema inhibition (61.41%; $p < 0.01$) suppression of the exudate (38.09% $p < 0.01$) and granuloma mass forms (53.47% $p < 0.01$) [14].

Evaluation of Anti-inflammatory activity in terms of stabilization of HRBC membrane by suppressing hypotonicity-induced lysis of the erythrocyte membrane. A comparative analysis was done to evaluate the extract's suppression of hemolysis and protection from hemolysis vs the conventional medication diclofenac sodium. The extract inhibited hemolysis, the most at 2000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, with only $4.11 \pm 1.8\%$ hemolysis detected. Diclofenac sodium reduced hemolysis to $32.6 \pm 4.9\%$ at the same concentration. The root extract performed well as an anti-inflammatory agent [15].

4.3 Hepatoprotective activity

Anindya Bagchi and colleagues discovered that a larger dose of methanol extract of *A. mexicana* root (400 mg/kg) had notable hepatoprotective benefits by raising antioxidant enzyme levels and regulating liver enzyme, protein, lipid profile, and cytokine levels. Eupatilin, identified using GC-MS analysis, was revealed to be a possible bioactive molecule with hepatoprotective

properties [16].The hepatoprotective effects of an ethyl acetate extract of *Argemone mexicana* Linn (200 and 400 mg/kg body weight) on rats treated with carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄). The treatment had significant hepatoprotective effects ($P<0.001$), as proved by lowered blood enzyme activity (AST, ALT, ALP, and serum Bilirubin) and almost normal histological architecture of the liver in treated groups compared to controls [17].The hepatoprotective effectiveness of a chloroform extract of *Argemone mexicana* (100 and 200 mg/kg) was tested against paracetamol-induced hepatotoxicity. Serum levels of glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT), glutamic-pyruvic transaminase (SGPT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), bilirubin, and triglycerides were determined. The protective action of *Argemone mexicana* Chloroform extract in the prevention of PCM-induced liver toxicity in rats was linked to a decrease in oxidative stress in hepatic tissues [18].

4.4 Anti diabetic

The study examined *Argemone mexicana*'s antidiabetic characteristics by inhibiting α -glucosidase and α -amylase, as well as determining glucose absorption capacity using yeast cells. Alpha-glucosidase inhibitors (AGIs) and alpha-amylase inhibitors (AAs) demonstrated maximal inhibition of 83.92% and 59.17%, respectively, at 100mg/ml. The glucose absorption capacity of yeast cells was enhanced from 0.07% to 19.89% by raising the concentration of the experimental sample from 0.78mg/ml to 100mg/ml [19].

Rout et al. reported that the hydro-alcoholic extract of the aerial parts of *A. mexicana* reduced fasting blood glucose levels in hyperglycemic wistar albino rats induced by streptozotocin at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg body weight, revealing the anti-diabetic activity of *Argemone mexicana* [20]. Aqueous extracts of aerial portions of the plant *A. mexicana* at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg body weight were evaluated for hypoglycemic action in alloxan-induced diabetic rats. It was proven by a significant reduction in blood glucose levels, cholesterol, creatinine, plasma urea, triacylglyceride, and improvement in body weight when compared to diabetic control and conventional medication treated rats [21].

4.5 Anticancer activity

The Trypan blue exclusion experiment was used to examine the cytotoxic effect on cells. Vinblastin at 20 μ g per well (24.5 nM) served as a control for the comparison of *A. mexicana* leaf and stem extracts. A variety of concentrations of methanolic and cold aqueous extracts of *A. mexicana* leaves and stems were tested on immortalized cell lines of A549, SiHa, and KB. At 300 μ g, *A. mexicana* extracts' cytotoxicity on the A549 cell line was greater to that of the KB and SiHa immortalized cell lines [22].The anticancer properties of *A. mexicana* leaf aqueous extract were evaluated against MCF-7 breast cancer cells at varying doses. MTT Assay and Trypan Blue Dye Exclusion Assay were used to examine cell viability and apoptosis induction. When compared to the untreated group, MCF-7 cells treated with *A. mexicana* extract showed a significant increase in apoptosis, suppression of growth, and proliferation when assessed for caspase activities [23].

The excellent cancer-preventive activity of *Argemone mexicana* Linn leaves was demonstrated by the ethanolic extract of the leaves using the DMBA/TPA technique to develop skin cancer in Swiss Albino mice. The investigations were conducted based on the NF- κ B (p65 subunit) signaling pathway, augmentation of TNF α -secretion, histology, haematological parameters, and the time period of in-tumor induction incidence. The extract's best dose for anticancer activity was found to be at 500 mg/kg bodyweight [24]. Cell viability was assessed using the MTT (methylthiazolyl diphenyl-tetrazolium bromide) test to determine the cytotoxicity efficacy of the ethyl acetate fraction of *A. mexicana* L. floral extract at varying doses against the HepG2 cell line. Significant cell viability was demonstrated by the fraction at 250 μ g/ml, or $28.11\pm 1.00^{**}$. With an IC₅₀ value of 72 ± 1.7 μ g/ml, the fraction was considered to have 50% cell viability [25]. Kishore Kumar Sarkar *et al.*, and group evaluated Cytotoxic activity of ethanolic extract of *Argemone mexicana* Linn. aerial parts, it was assessed through brine shrimp lethality bioassay. As concentration increased the rate of mortality as a percentage increased. Vincristine sulphate's LC₅₀ value was 0.364 μ g/ml, whereas the EAMA's was 51.0105 μ g/ml [26].

4.6 Anti-HIV Activity:

The entire *A. mexicana* plant was allowed to air dry before being turned into a methanol extract. In the H9 lymphocyte assay, the extract's (\pm)-6-acetyl dihydrochelerythrine and benzophenanthridine (an alkaloid) compounds showed effective anti-HIV activity, with an EC₅₀ value of 1.77 μ g/ml [27].

4.7 Diuretic Activity :

The diuretic action of the extract from *Argemone mexicana* leaves was assessed by measuring conductivity, pH, and urine production using conventional techniques. The extract at doses of 100 and 250 mg/kg, p.o., and conventional frusemide (20 mg/kg, i.p.) significantly ($P < 0.05$) enhanced urine output. Rats administered with 250 mg/kg of *Argemone mexicana* showed an increase in urine production [28]. The evaluation of Diuretic activity carried out by *Lipchitz et al.*, method and the parameters measured were urine volume, pH and electrolytes. Furosemide (20mg/kg) was taken as standard reference drug. Ethanolic extracts, chloroform extract and aqueous extract of *Argemone mexicana* leaves (200mg/kg (p.o)) have been shown a significant activity by an increase in all the parameters when compared to control [29].

4.8 Laxative activity

In rats, the extract from *Argemone mexicana* leaves boosted fecal production in a dose-dependent way. Compared to the control group, rats administered 100 mg/kg and 250 mg/kg of the extract produced noticeably more feces. The maximum impact was observed at 250 mg/kg, which was comparable to sodium picosulfate (5 mg/kg), a common laxative medication [30].

4.9 Other pharmacological effects:

4.9.1 Neuropharmacological action

Evaluation of neuropharmacological action conducted on Swiss albino mice and were given methanolic and ethyl acetate extracts of the whole plant *Argemone mexicana* (Papaveraceae) at doses of 100 mg/kg, 200 mg/kg, and 400 mg/kg b.w. for CNS-related activities. The extracts CNS depressant activity was assessed, and both extracts exhibited significant central and peripheral nociceptive activity. Additionally, the animals' motor activity and fall-off time on a rotating rod were significantly reduced, and their sedative effects were observed by intensifying the phenobarbitone-induced sleeping time. These findings suggested that the extracts of *Argemone mexicana* have analgesic, anxiolytic, and sedative effects [31].

4.9.2 Anti-Urolithiatic Activity

The ability of *Argemone mexicana* to inhibit urolithiatic was evaluated, the degree of inhibition of anti-urolithiasis capacity against preformed calcium oxalate crystal was assessed using extracts from L. leaves. The methanol leaf extract of *A. mexicana* demonstrated significant inhibition (72.26%) in comparison to the standard cystone drug (62.96%) in the nucleation assay, and at a concentration of 100 mg/ml, it also demonstrated significant inhibition (77.24%) in comparison to cystone (69.33%) in the aggregation assay. The ability of *A. mexicana* leaf extracts to dissolve calcium oxalate crystals was amply demonstrated by the microscopic assay [32].

4.9.3 Analgesic activity

Kishore Kumar Sarkar *et al.*, and group evaluated analgesic activity of ethanolic extract of *Argemone mexicana* aerial parts peripheral and central analgesic activities were evaluated by acetic acid-induced writhing test, formalin-induced paw licking test, tail immersion test and hot plate test. both lower and higher doses of extract showed significant percentage inhibition of writhing as well as paw licking respectively (* $P < 0.05$, vs. control). extract at the doses of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg revealed significant latency response (* $P < 0.05$, vs. control) in delayed phase in both tail immersion as well as hot plate test [33].

4.9.4 Antidiarrheal Activity

Kishore Kumar Sarkar *et al.*, and group evaluated In vivo castor oil-induced diarrheal model and magnesium sulphate induced diarrheal model in mice with ethanolic extract of *Argemone mexicana* Linn. aerial parts, and were utilized for the assessment of anti-diarrheal activity. Significant percentage inhibition (* $P < 0.05$, vs. control) of diarrhea was exposed by 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg of EAMA in in vivo diarrheal models [34].

4.9.5 Antibacterial Activity

Using the disc diffusion assay, Kishore Kumar Sarkar *et al.* and their team assessed the antibacterial activity of an ethanolic extract of the aerial portions of *Argemone mexicana* Linn. At concentrations of 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ and 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$, EAMA demonstrated antibacterial activity against both gram positive and gram negative bacterial strains [35]. The broth dilution method and the agar well diffusion method were used to determine the MICs and antibacterial activity of the cold aqueous and methanolic extracts of *A. mexicana* L leaves, respectively. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* were all inhibited in their growth by the extracts. The antibacterial potentiality of *A. mexicana* L extracts was compared with Streptomycin - the reference antibiotic used in this study [36].

The antimicrobial screening of the plant extracts of the leaves and seeds of *A. mexicana* on *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *B. subtilis* revealed that the seed extracts were more effective than those of the leaf extracts. Methanol extracts of *A. mexicana* (leaves and seeds) showed considerably more efficacy than the hot aqueous and cold aqueous extracts against all the reference bacterial strains. The methanol extracts of *A. mexicana* (leaves and seeds) showed maximum antibacterial activity against *P. aeruginosa*, followed by *E. coli*, *B. subtilis*, and *S. aureus*. On the contrary, aqueous extracts (cold and hot) of *A. mexicana* seeds showed maximum activity against *B. subtilis*, followed by *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, and *S. aureus*. Again, cold aqueous extract of *A. mexicana* leaves showed highest efficacy against *P. aeruginosa* followed by *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, and *S. aureus* whereas in case of hot aqueous extract of *A. mexicana* leaves, maximum sensitivity was shown against *E. coli*, followed by *B. subtilis*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* [37].

Argemone mexicana L. (Papaveraceae) seed extracts were tested for their antibacterial efficacy against a few pathogenic bacterial strains. The antibacterial activity of seed chloroform extract against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria varied. It was discovered that the chloroform extract was more effective than the other extracts against every test bacterium. MIC values for drug-resistant strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were 3.0 and 2.0 mg/ml, respectively [38].

4.9.6 Anthelmintic activity

The ethanolic extract of *Argemone mexicana* Linn was tested for anthelmintic activity by Kishore Kumar Sarkar *et al.* and team. It was performed on *Paramphistomum cervi* (Trematoda) aerial components. Degree of activity, including intestinal worm paralysis and death at different dosages (25 mg/ml and 50 mg/ml). Comparison with standard albendazole (15 mg/ml) revealed a dose-dependent effect [39].

4.9.7 Aphrodisiac Potential

The aphrodisiac potentials of ethanol extract of *Argemone mexicana* L was evaluated on sexually inactive male rats. Sexually inactive male rats were treated with ethanol extract of *A. mexicana* (EEAM) at 1 g/kg daily oral dose for 28 days. The oral dosing of EEAM has significantly enhanced the orientation of males towards female by increase in ano-genital investigatory behavior, frequencies of mount, intromission, and ejaculation ($P < 0.01$). The latencies of mount, intromission and ejaculation were significantly decreased ($P < 0.05$) The extract produced marked variation in sexual behavior characteristics and was able to elevate the serum testosterone levels ($P < 0.01$) assessed with that of sildenafil citrate [40].

4.9.8 Antiandrogenic potential

Argemone mexicana leaves were extracted in six different solvents with increasing polarity: petroleum ether, benzene, chloroform, ethanol, cold water, and hot water. The anti-androgenic efficacy of various solvent extracts of *A. mexicana* leaves

was assessed by measuring in vitro ovarian 3β - and 17β - hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase (HSDH). All six solvent extracts tested decreased ovarian 3β - and 17β -HSDH activities. However, the ethanolic extract of *A. mexicana* leaves considerably reduced ovarian 3β - and 17β -HSDH activities relative to the control [41].

4.9.9 Female reproductive system

The effect of a freshly extracted root of *Argemone mexicana* on the female reproductive system evaluation revealed the increase in body and uterine weights somewhat in the treated group. The uterus microscopic structure showed unaltered histoarchitecture with respect to myometrial and perimetrial thickness in treated and control groups, whereas the endometrial thickness was observed to be higher in the treated group [42].

4.9.10 Anti-asthmatic activity

The anti-asthmatic activity of an ethanolic extract of *Argemone mexicana* stem, as well as its chloroform and ethyl acetate fractions, was tested in vitro models (isolated guinea pig ileum and isolated guinea pig tracheal chain preparations) and in vivo models (histamine and acetylcholine induced bronchospasm in guinea pigs and milk induced eosinophilia in mouse models). At a dosage of 10mg, the ethanolic extract of *Argemone mexicana* and its ethyl acetate fraction markedly reduced histamine-induced contraction of isolated guinea pig ileum and trachea chain preparations [43].

4.9.11 Antifungal activity

Two fungal strains, *Fusarium moniliforme* and *Aspergillus niger*, were treated with various *Argemone mexicana* extracts. As an antifungal agent, *Argemone mexicana* ethyl acetate extract outperformed *Argemone mexicana* ethanolic extract [44]. More NV et al. and colleagues discovered that both cold aqueous and methanolic extracts of *A. mexicana* stem and leaves prevented the growth of *Mucor indicus*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Penicillium notatum*. The extract's antifungal activity was comparable with amphotericin B [45].

4.9.12 Anxiolytic effect

The ethanolic extract of *Argemone mexicana* at 200 mg/kg and alkaloid-enriched extract (200 μ g/kg) displayed anxiolytic-like effects similar to diazepam at 2 mg/kg by EPM test, without influencing locomotor activity. Meanwhile, picrotoxin treatment inhibited the anti-anxiety effects of the plant's alkaloid-rich extract [46].

5. Conclusion

The medicinal plants contain an ample range of secondary metabolites, which have been recognized as active principles to cure diverse diseases. *Argemone mexicana*, a plant of Papaveraceae family contains numerous astonishing phytoconstituents. In this chapter, we have reviewed the plant profile, habitate and botany, pharmacological activity of various extract. The plant also revealed numerous pharmacological properties such as analgesic, anti-inflammation, antidiabetic, anticancer, hepatoprotective, wound recovering, anti HIV activity, antibacterial, antifungal, and anthelmintic activity and many more. Hence the paramount importance of this review is to emphasize the need for plant based drug on the socio economic purpose which gives a hope to the pharmacologists to develop novel drugs with no side effects. From the above review of the plant *Argemone mexicana*, steps should be undertaken for conservation and proper utilization of such beneficial plants.

Author contributions

Aishwarya R Kurdekar, conceived, designed, and wrote the review article; Dr. A.M. Krupanidhi checked and supplemented the contents of the table; checked for spelling errors and revised grammatical errors.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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